

(c) 4,4', 6,6'-Tetramethoxy-2,2'-dihydroxy-3,3'-di(ω -benzoylacetyl)-biphenyl

A mixture of 4,4', 6,6'-tetramethoxy-2,2'-dibenzoyloxy-3,3'-diacetylbiphenyl (5 g), acetone (200 ml) and potassium carbonate (50 g) was refluxed on a water bath for 30 hr. Acetone was removed by distillation on water bath. The residue was added to water. The precipitated 4,4', 6,6'-tetramethoxy-2,2'-dihydroxy-3,3'-di(ω -benzoylacetyl)-biphenyl was filtered and recrystallised from dilute alcohol as yellow needles, m.p. 178°–179° (found: C, 67.86; H, 4.95; $C_{34}H_{30}O_{10}$ requires C, 68.23; H, 5.017%).

(d) I-5, II-5, I-7, II-7-Tetramethoxy [I-8, II-8] biflavone

4,4', 6,6'-tetramethoxy-2,2'-dihydroxy-3,3'-di(ω -benzoylacetyl)-biphenyl (2 g) was dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (20 ml) and kept at room temperature. After 8 hr the solution was poured into water. The precipitated biflavone was filtered and recrystallised from dilute alcohol as yellow needles, m.p. 203°–204°, λ_{max} in ethanol at 270 and 310 nm. (Found: C, 72.35; H, 4.55; OMe, 21.2; Mol. wt. (Mass spectrometry), 562; $C_{34}H_{28}O_8$ requires C, 72.61; H, 4.63; OMe, 22.07%; Mol. wt., 562).

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Chemical Investigation of *Canthium diococcum*

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THE benzene extract of the bark of the plant *Canthium diococcum* after column chromatography yielded a number of terpenoids. One of these compounds, $C_{30}H_{50}O$, m.p. 185°–86°, formed

an acetate, $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$, m.p. 225°, and these have been characterized as α -amyrin and its acetate respectively by comparison of m.p., TLC and IR spectra with authentic samples. The alcoholic extract of the bark yielded a saponin which on acid hydrolysis gave an acid, $C_{30}H_{48}O_3$, m.p. 306°–8°, which formed a methyl ester, $C_{31}H_{50}O_3$, m.p. 196°–8°. These have been characterized as oleanolic acid and methyl oleanolate respectively by comparison of m.p., TLC and IR spectra with authentic samples.

Experimental

Air-dried powdered bark (1 kg) was extracted successively with benzene and ethanol (95%) for 48 hr in a Soxhlet apparatus. The benzene extract was separated into acid and neutral fractions in the usual way and the latter was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel (200 g) and eluted with different solvents. Benzene eluate gave a fraction which was crystallized from ethanol, $C_{30}H_{50}O$, m.p. 185°–86°. It was heated with acetic anhydride and pyridine on steam bath and worked up in the usual way. Crystallization from ethanol gave an acetate, $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$, m.p. 225°.

The ethanolic extract was concentrated by distillation and the crude saponin was precipitated by addition of excess ether. The crude saponin gave copious lather when shaken with water. It was dissolved in ethanol (200 ml) and 40 ml of conc. hydrochloric acid was added and refluxed on steam bath for an hour. This was then diluted with water and the precipitated sapogenin was extracted with ether which was separated into acid and neutral fractions in the usual way with 1% aqueous caustic potash solution. The acid fraction was chromatographed over silica gel and the $CHCl_3/MeOH$ (95:5 v/v) eluate gave a fraction which crystallized from methanol, $C_{31}H_{50}O_3$, m.p. 196°–8°.

Satisfactory analytical data were obtained for the compounds reported.

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Triterpenoids. XLII. Further Studies on the Structure of Lantanolic Acid

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BARUA and co-workers earlier^{1,2} proposed the structure (I) for lantanolic acid, a new triterpene

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